

Consultation European Commission for the Forthcoming Data Union Strategy. Views of the DATAMITE Consortium.

THE CURRENT & THE FORTHCOMING DATA UNION STRATEGY

The current European Strategy for Data contributes towards the creation of a single market for data that ensures global competitiveness and data sovereignty for Europe, thereby also leading to the creation of Common European Data Spaces. Consequently, vast amount of data is constantly becoming available for use in the economy and society, while also keeping companies and individuals generating the data in control. To further safeguard EU's role as a leader in the global data economy, the Strategy is particularly concentrated on: adopting legislative measures on data governance, access and reuse (e.g., for business-to-government data sharing for the public interest); making data more widely accessible through the opening up of high-value publicly held datasets across the EU, allowing their reuse for free; investing billions of euros in a European High Impact Project to develop data processing infrastructures, data sharing tools, architectures and governance mechanisms enabling data sharing and federating energy-efficient and trustworthy cloud infrastructures and related services; enabling access to secure, fair and competitive cloud services by facilitating the set-up of a procurement marketplace for data processing services.

In view of the launched Open Consultation on the forthcoming New European Strategy for Data, the following paragraphs are concerned with evaluating considerations drawn from the experience of DATAMITE, but also general views beyond its context, that shall serve as guiding points when deciding on the pillars of the New Strategy.

THE DATAMITE PROJECT IN SHORT

DATAMITE is a project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe programme and coordinated by the ITI – Technological Institute of Informatics. DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve DATA Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetisation potential at two levels. At internal level, users shall have tools to improve quality management of their data, the adherence to

FAIR principles, and is going to be able to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project generates. Therefore, data shall become trustable and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.

At external level, keeping users in control of their data shall provide new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders. The architecture envisioned for DATAMITE enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential instructor on their onboarding of SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE's solutions shall function as a catalyst to boost data monetisation in the European productive fabric.

DATAMITE Use Cases (UCs) differentiate in two key parts, **how data is treated and how data is shared**. In all UCs, **data governance, quality or security modules** are used, thereby aiming at improving how data is managed within companies, how good data is, as well as how interoperable data is across organisational boundaries. The six core pilots are as follows: Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with DIH Support (represented by GIDITEK, ITI, EGI); Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange (represented by OTE, EGI); Offering Data to Service Providers with Dataspaces (represented by HEDNO, CERTH); Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data (represented by E-REDES); Connecting EDWIN to Data Markets (represented by WODR, PSNC, AGREGO); Connecting Mistral to the EU AI-ON-DEMAND Platform (represented by CINECA, UCC).

THOUGHTS ON INTEROPERABILITY AND THE EC'S PROPOSED THREE PILLARS – THE PERSPECTIVE OF DATAMITE

First and foremost, **Enhancing Cross-Sectoral and Intra-Sectoral European Data Spaces' Interoperability** shall be prioritized and promoted by the forthcoming Data Strategy. More particularly, DATAMITE proposes to the European Commission (hereinafter "EC") to prioritise the development of a common, harmonised approach, as a prerequisite to leverage the data spaces development, thereby also allowing for the evolution of sectoral regulations, **similarly to the existing model in the health sector**. Taking the energy sector as a use case exemplifying the discussed need, based on the tests performed between DATAMITE and the existing energy data spaces, the following conclusions have been drawn.

Firstly, **lack of technical and semantic interoperability persists** due to divergent functional architecture models, namely, in relation to **incorporation of the GAIA-X, IDS and Data Spaces Protocol requisites in the architectures**. Due to the divergent technology implementations across different energy data spaces, the potential for convergence and cross-border collaboration is thus being undermined.

Consequently, it shall be acknowledged that without a common framework and shared standards, there is a risk of deepening the silos rather than bridging them. Therefore, it is **essential that all sectoral data spaces are built with interoperability at their core, guided by a shared European reference architecture**. Furthermore, **user involvement and co-creation** are critical for ensuring that data spaces remain adaptive, inclusive, and fit for purpose in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

DATAMITE thus recommends that the **EC adopts a coordinated, horizontal strategy, to enable the technical, semantic, and legal interoperability of data spaces from the outset**, thereby unlocking the full value of data for all sectors and citizens.

As the EC is proposing to base the forthcoming Data Union Strategy on the below-referenced three main pillars, the same are discussed from the point of experience within DATAMITE.

I) Improving and Facilitating Secure Private and Public Data Sharing

To enhance private and public data sharing at European level, the following points for action must be addressed:

- **Clear data governance frameworks** that define roles, responsibilities, and access rights for all stakeholders.
- **Interoperability-by-design** through common standards and reference architectures, developed collaboratively but flexibly recognising national and regional specificities.
- **Support for secure, value-driven data exchange**, including mechanisms for trusted anonymisation and cybersecurity.
- In a **check & balances** manner, data spaces themselves, and not only technology providers, shall be responsible for ensuring/certifying that participants share data in a legally and ethically compliant manner.
- **Common Data Monetization Framework EU-wide is needed, including further unification towards a common EU-wide regulatory approach.**

II) Simplifying the Regulatory Regime, Improving Consistency, and Fostering Application

To enhance the stance of the existing regulatory framework, the following must be ensured:

- **Light-touch, principle-based regulation**, focused on key outcomes like transparency, accountability, and interoperability.
- **Promote and develop regulatory sandboxes** and pilot-friendly frameworks that allow different stakeholders to test data-sharing models in real conditions before scaling.
- **Soft law instruments**, e.g.: guidelines; codes of conduct; or common reference architectures – co-created with the sector and updated iteratively. Ready-to-use templates for organisations, elaborating on and harmonising the efforts at national level, shall also be encouraged, as well as the creation of straightforward and easy

to apply resources, including checklists, practical guidelines for compliance in action, etc.

- **Measures for enhancing consistency of the application and enforcement by national authorities**, e.g.: collection of positions by national authorities on priority issues taken in national guidance and decisions, including court judgements, thus producing publications in a “case law” manner, thereby assisting organisations in understanding concrete positions taken concerning interpretation; ongoing monitoring to further complement guidelines, to ensure effectiveness and consistent application including through reviews of the same, as well as through targeted coordinated enforcement actions and strategies; continued effort in aligning domestic and EU-level guidance in cases of identified inconsistencies; develop common practices, methodologies, tools and common actions for greater harmonisation of enforcement.
- **Cross-Regulatory Measures to Improve Consistency**, e.g.: preparing joint guidelines together with regulators, as deemed appropriate, in order to ensure consistency in the application of different legal frameworks; enabling effective and structured cooperation amongst regulators to exchange experience and to address legal and practical challenges in cross-regulatory cooperation on concrete cases; fostering proactively meetings between domestic regulators and relevant EU bodies, as deemed relevant.

The above-referenced measures shall reduce the overall complexity of regulations, currently constituting more of a hurdle for smaller actors, in terms of ensuring compliance, as usually only big companies have in-house lawyers. As many SMEs do not understand or are oftentimes not even aware of legal & ethics requirements, this shall thus enable all stakeholders, including SMEs, to identify their obligations and ensure compliance. On the other hand, the proposed measures shall also improve overall consistency, application, as well as enforcement of the regulatory framework.

III) Accelerating the Development of New Systems and Applications

To enhance systems and applications development at the European level, the following must be ensured:

- **Avoid mandates** of specific platforms or architectures which risk locking stakeholders into rigid or costly solutions.
- **Support reference frameworks** that allow diverse systems to interconnect, rather than replace what works locally.
- **Encourage the development of open APIs**, common data models, and shared ontologies which make it easier to build interoperable apps and services.

**FURTHER THOUGHTS ON THE STANCE OF DATA AS A PRODUCTION
FACTOR –
POLICY DELIBERATIONS CONCERNING EXISTING LEGISLATION**

The economic relevance of digital data, as well as its rapidly growing volume, has led to the emergence of several data market regulations: the GDPR, the Data Act, the Digital Markets Act, the Artificial Intelligence Act, and the Regulation on the European Health Data Space, with all of these major laws aiming to open up access to data locked up in technical silos, thereby facilitating the emergence of data markets and stimulating the development of innovative data-driven services. The following paragraphs until the end of the paper are inspired by and follow the analogy of rationale examined by B. Martens.¹

The perception of data as a production factor driving international competitiveness² has been gaining popularity, and acknowledging the stance of data regimes in the US with that of China, the former being rather light and open, and the other more centralised, with that of the EU, which stands somewhere in the middle, in that it encompasses both private rights and data-sharing obligations, it is evident that regime choices mirror domestic political and ideological choices. Yet, the said regime choices have economic implications, too. As Henna Virkkunen, Commission Vice President for Tech Sovereignty, Security and Democracy, has been given the task of improving EU data market policies and proposing “a European Data Union Strategy drawing on existing data rules to ensure a simplified and coherent framework to share data seamlessly”³, the following question has been awaiting answer: **How may a data-market regime maximising the efficient use of data as an economic production factor be designed?**

1 Martens, B., “Using data as a production factor: policy ideas for a new EU data strategy”, Policy Brief 01/2025, Bruegel [2025] <<https://www.bruegel.org/policy-brief/using-data-production-factor-policy-ideas-new-eu-data-strategy>> accessed on 01 July 2025.

2 Diebold G. “Comparing Data Policy Priorities Around the World”, Center for Data Innovation [2023].

3 Ursula von der Leyen, “Mission Letter to Henna Virkkunen” [2024] <https://commission.europa.eu/document/3b537594-9264-4249-a912-5b102b7b49a3_en> accessed on 01 July 2025.

In comparison to physical goods which are rival, data is non-rival, as it can be used by multiple parties, for multiple purposes, and simultaneously. Consequently, the nature or non-rivalry generates externalities or spillovers, i.e., value that can potentially be generated by parties other than those involved in the original data collection. **Therefore, a regime that maximises the value of data should enable multiple uses and externalities.** Exclusive property or control by a single party is thus not a viable option. Having said that, it is crucial to acknowledge that unless these externalities may prove to be beneficial for the controlling parties, the latter have no incentive to share data, and that limits the value that society as a whole can extract from the data. On the other hand, private rights are not to be excluded, as data collectors need to earn a return on their investment in data-collection costs. Yet, the marginal cost of data collection is oftentimes close to zero, particularly in cases when data is a by-product of ongoing activities and transactions, in which case, re-use by others and for other purposes is not a disincentive for the original data collection. In addition, as data is usually co-produced between at least two parties, e.g., buyers and sellers, both sides may claim blockage or limitation of access to and use of the data by third parties. The GDPR, e.g., grants personal-data collectors with some rights, as well as other rights to the natural persons whose behavioural data is collected. On the other hand, data holders are being granted with some exclusive rights by the Data Act, to charge a price for third-party access, with that potentially leading to blocking data markets.

All in all, balancing between private rights and the wider benefits for society of data re-use is not an easy endeavour. **A central question is thus how more efficient data-driven product and services markets may be achieved. Data markets shall thus be examined from a wider social welfare perspective.**

Data non-rivalry generates two potential sources of economic benefits: Economies of scope from the re-use of data⁴, and Economies of scope in data

⁴ Panzar, J.C. and R.D. Willig "Economies of scope", *American Economic Review* 71(2): 268–272 [1981].

aggregation⁵. Concerning **economies of scope from the re-use of data**, it shall be acknowledged that once collected, data can be re-used by many parties for many purposes simultaneously, e.g., for other services and/or by other service providers, to offer complementary and competing services. Although re-use by others shall not functionally impact the original use, it may have an economic impact on the parties that co-generated the original data. Regarding the **economies of scope in data aggregation**, it shall be acknowledged that data from many different sources may be pooled and aggregated, as oftentimes it becomes more valuable when aggregated across more users. Pooled data may particularly reveal patterns and deliver service insights that cannot be extracted from fragmented datasets or individual data.⁶

Finding partners to share the data with, or to arrange complementary inputs to generate value, may be difficult, and the willingness to pay for data may vary between users and service applications. In addition, **facilitating exploration of this value may require specific data-market design**⁷. Moreover, not only is it hard to determine the value that data contributes to a data-driven service but negotiated market outcomes often depend on the market power of the partners. Furthermore, data transfers often require intermediary institutions that define data formats and transfer protocols and set the conditions for access and re-use⁸, and while this may be simple for bilateral data sharing, it is complex for data aggregation or pooling between many parties. **The conclusion that transaction costs often stand in the way of realising the societal value of data may thus be drawn.**

Apart from simplifying the European Union's range of data market laws into a more coherent framework accompanied by additional guidelines, **at the heart of the new**

⁵ Bajari, P., V. Chernozhukov, A. Hortaçsu and J. Suzuki "The impact of big data on firm performance: An empirical investigation", *AEA Papers and Proceedings* 109: 33–37 [2019].

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Bergemann, D. and A. Bonatti "Markets for information: an introduction", *CEPR Discussion Paper DP13148*, Centre for Economic Policy Research [2018].

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Martens, B. "An institutional economics approach to data spaces as data market intermediaries" [2024] <<https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4731126>> accessed on 01 July 2025.

approach to the forthcoming Data Union Strategy should also be the non-rival nature of data, i.e., so that it may be used by many parties, for multiple purposes, and simultaneously. The latter shall allow for creating the potential for economic efficiency gains from the re-use and aggregation of data. Since exclusive private data control rights and high transaction costs may preclude the realisation of the said gains, economic criteria against which existing data market regulations may be evaluated, shall be defined, and the same lead to the below-referenced summarised recommendations for improving existing EU data regulations, which **at the moment exhibit tension between exclusive private rights and the realisation of the wider societal value of data, and may thus necessitate the pursue of balance involving certain redistribution of the efficiency gains between data users and the original data collectors.**⁹

- Re-use of personal data is facilitated by the EU GDPR. As high transaction costs prevent meaningful exercise of informed consent, **machine-readable consent notices and real-time data transfers** could be viable solution.
- With due regard to the robust governance regime for health data re-use and pooling that maximises incentives for data-driven innovation that the European Health Data Space possesses, **analogous regime should be applied to other industrial data space initiatives.**
- Even though access and re-use of product data is facilitated by the Data Act, exclusive licensing rights for data holders and monopolistic pricing of third-party data transfers reduce its impact. **To achieve a truly horizontal data-market regulation, the application of the Data Act shall be widened to services data.**
- Several obligations for platforms to grant users access to their own data are defined by the Digital Markets Act. To increase market competition, making this market data sharable between competing platforms shall thus be considered. For

⁹ Martens, B., "Using data as a production factor: policy ideas for a new EU data strategy", Policy Brief 01/2025, Bruegel [2025] <<https://www.bruegel.org/policy-brief/using-data-production-factor-policy-ideas-new-eu-data-strategy>> accessed on 01 July 2025.

example, an extension of the current obligations to encompass a wider set of platform interaction data, beyond first-party “own” direct interaction data shall be initiated, since platforms have the said data at their disposal but are oftentimes reluctant to share it with sellers. As, e.g., platforms are usually browsed by consumers looking at several products/services at a time, prior to taking a decision, the generated browsing data may avail useful information for sellers to better understand their competitors.

As has been observed, since the trade-offs between individual and social welfare are decided by policymakers, some tend to leave it to the market and individual bargaining power, as in the case of US, others have inclination towards the collective side, as China, whilst the EU is somewhere in the middle of the two regimes. Yet, it must be noted that the two sides are not necessarily opposed, and that **the pursue of social welfare does not necessarily imply weakening private rights to data**. In fact, **technologies may be leveraged that can combine the two objectives**, e.g., through federated learning techniques in AI and machine learning, as well as various types of privacy sandboxes in personal data protection.¹⁰

CONCLUDING REMARKS

All in all, as has been observed further actions concerning the stance of interoperability are needed. In addition, clear data governance frameworks, support for secure and value-driven data exchange, as well as Common Data Monetization Standards EU-Wide, are awaiting to be addressed. Of course, overall simplification of the regulatory regime, improving consistency, and fostering application, are all steps of an imperative importance, too. Finally, enhancing systems and applications development at the European level, the following must be ensured: avoid mandates of specific platforms or architectures which may lead to locking stakeholders into rigid or costly solutions;

¹⁰ Ibid.

encourage reference frameworks that allow diverse systems to interconnect, instead of replacing what works locally; and, encourage support the development of open APIs, common data models, as well as shared ontologies which make it easier to build interoperable apps and services.

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